

while noticeable activity was recorded against *Alternaria brassicae*.

TABLE 1—CHARACTERISTICS OF 2-AMINO-4-PHENYL-5-P-AZOBENZENE SULPHOANAMIDO THIAZOLES

Sl. No.	R	m.p. °C	Yield %	R _f
1.	Hydrogen	246-247	85	0.88
2.	Guanidinyl	238-240	90	0.76
3.	Acetyl	202-208	85	0.90
4.	2-(1-Phenyl pyrazolyl)	199-201	80	0.87
5.	3-(5-Methyl isoxazolyl)	201-208	80	0.94
6.	2-Thiazolyl	225-227	90	0.88
7.	2-(5-Methyl 1,3,4-thiadiazolyl)	230-282	85	0.74
8.	4-(2,6-Dimethyl pyrimidyl)	233-235	80	0.94
9.	2-(Pyrimidyl)	228-235	95	0.78
10.	2-(4,6-Dimethyl pyrimidyl)	209-211	80	0.72

All compounds gave consistent nitrogen analysis.

Anticancer activity test was done at Tata Cancer Research Institute, Bombay against mouse tumour system P 388 but all the compounds were found inactive.

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Constituents of *Rhus punjabensis*

MOHAMMED KAMIL*, IQBAL AHMAD and M. ILYAS

Department of Chemistry, Aligarh Muslim University, Aligarh

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FAMILY Anacardiaceae which consists of 73 genera and about 600 species is rich for its biflavonoidic constituents. The genus *Rhus*, one of the largest genera of the family, is chiefly distributed in the warm temperature region of both hemispheres extending into the tropical and cold temperature region. An attempt has been made to study the

complex mixture of biflavonoids in the leave extracts of *Rhus punjabensis* (procured from Gopeshwar Hills, Chamoli Distt., India).

The phenolic extractives after preliminary purification and tlc examination on silica gel using benzene-pyridine-acetic acid (36:9:5)¹ developing solvent showed two bands, labelled as RPI and RPII. They were separated by preparative thin layer chromatography.

Although RPI was chromatographically homogeneous, on methylation and tlc examination it was found to be a mixture of three methyl ethers, one major and two minor ones. The major methyl ether labelled as RPIMII was separated by preparative tlc, and characterized as agathisflavone hexamethyl ether, m.p. 162-64°, by spectral analysis and comparison with authentic sample^{2,3}. The two minor methyl ethers, obtained by methylation of RPI, were identified as amentoflavone and robustaflavone hexamethyl ethers by comparison with authentic samples (R_f values, characteristic fluorescence in uv light and co-*tlc*)^{4,5}.

RPII was identified as hinokiflavone, i.e. 1-5, 11-5, 1-7, 11-7, 11-4' pentahydroxy (1-4'-O-11-8) flavone by its spectral properties as well as those of its methyl ether, m.p. 260-64° and acetate, m.p. 237-40°.

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Synthesis and Ion-Exchange Properties of Thermally Stable Stannic Silico Selenite: Separation of Cu²⁺ from Zn²⁺ and Mn²⁺

S. D. SHARMA* and B. C. LATHE

Department of Chemistry, Hindu College, Moradabad-244 001

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SYNTHETIC inorganic ion-exchangers are found to be thermally more stable than their organic counterparts but the search for materials with still greater thermal stability continues. The thermal stability of silica (SiO₂.xH₂O), a naturally occurring weak inorganic ion-exchanger, is very high. Literature reveals that silica has been used in synthesising

* Address for correspondence: A-82, Gandhi Nagar, Moradabad-244 001.

double salts such as titanium phosphate silicate and zirconium phosphate silicate^{2,3}. No such studies has been reported on stannic silico selenite. It was therefore decided to synthesise this material at different pH and to study its ion-exchange properties and thermal behaviour.

Experimental

Stannic chloride pentahydrate (PPH, Poland), silica gel coarse (B.D.H., England) and sodium selenite (Riedel, Germany) were used. All other chemicals were of analytical reagents grade.

X-ray, ir, tga and pH measurements were performed on Debye-Scherrer powder X-ray diffractometer, Perkin Elmer spectrometer model 157, F.C.I. (Sindri) thermobalance and Systronics digital pH meter, respectively. Shaking was done with Toshniwal electronic shaker.

Synthesis of the exchanger :

0.1 M aqueous solution of $\text{SiO}_2 \cdot x\text{H}_2\text{O}$ was prepared in minimum quantity of NaOH and added with constant stirring to 0.1 M aqueous solution of $\text{SnCl}_4 \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and 0.1 M aqueous solution of Na_2SeO_3 in the volume ratio 1 : 1 : 1. Different samples (Table 1) were obtained by varying the pH, precipitation temperature and drying temperature. Ammonia solution (density=0.880) or HCl were added dropwise with constant shaking to adjust the pH in the desired alkaline or acidic ranges, respectively. In all the cases a white gelatinous precipitate was obtained which was allowed to stand for 24 hr at room temperature. It was then washed by decantation, filtered off and washed with the demineralised water. The gel was dried at different temperatures.

The dry product broke down into small particles when immersed in water. The exchanger was converted into hydrogen form by treatment with 1.0 M nitric acid and finally washed with demineralised water to remove the excess of acid and was again dried.

Chemical composition :

0.20 g of the exchanger (Sample 3) was dissolved in HCl. Insoluble silica was filtered, washed, dried at 100° for 2 hr, thus retaining a small water content (0.18 mole $\text{H}_2\text{O}/\text{SiO}_2$)⁴ and weighed as such. The filtrate was reduced with lead and tin was titrated with potassium dichromate⁵. Selenium was separated by sulphur dioxide treatment and determined gravimetrically as selenium metal⁶. The Sn : Si : Se ratio was found to be 2.6 : 1 : 1.2.

Results and Discussion

Sample 3 was chosen for further studies because of its high ion-exchange capacity and its total regain on regeneration. The reproducible nature of the material was tested by preparing and using it again under the same conditions. The exchanger is fairly stable in water and dilute mineral acids. Small portion of the material dissolved in 0.1 N NaOH in 2 days. To study the regeneration phenomenon of the exchanger, samples in K^+ form were converted into H^+ form by passing 100 ml 1 M HNO_3 over the column filled with 1.0 g exchanger. The flow rate was 8-9 drops/min. The column was washed with distilled water after the acid treatment to remove all traces of unused acid. The ion-exchange capacity of these regenerated samples was measured by the column method. Results (Table 1) show considerable regeneration for all the samples while for sample 3 there is total regeneration and so this material can be used more than once for all practical purposes. Stannic silico selenite samples are amorphous in nature as no line was observed in the X-ray spectra. This has been shown by X-ray diffraction powder patterns which were obtained with nickel-filtered $\text{Cu}-\text{K}_\alpha$ radiations. The pH titration curve shows a monofunctional behaviour similar to other amorphous inorganic ion-exchangers. Infrared spectra for the sample in H^+ form was obtained by the KBr disc method. A very strong band in the 3800-2900 cm^{-1} region with a maxima at 3400 cm^{-1} represents the free water and OH^- groups. The band in the 1700-1500 cm^{-1} region is characteristic of interstitial water molecules. The band in the 900-700 cm^{-1} region may be due to the selenite group. These bands are similar to those reported for stannic selenite⁷. In addition to these three bands, a fourth band with its maxima at 1100 cm^{-1} shows the presence of Si-O-Si bonding.

The thermal behaviour of the material was studied by heating the samples in H^+ form for 1 hr at different temperatures upto 800° in a muffle furnace. The ion-exchange capacity of the heated samples was measured. The results recorded in Table 2 show nearly 30% gain in ion-exchange capacity at 100° and this trend continues upto 400° where

TABLE 1—CONDITIONS OF PREPARATION, ORIGINAL AND REGENERATED EXCHANGE CAPACITY OF STANNIC SILICO SELENITE SAMPLES (MIXING RATIO v/v : 1 : 1 : 1)

Sample No.	Precipitation pH	Precipitation temp. °C	Drying temp. °C	Colour of beads	Ion-exchange capacity for K^+ (meq/g)	
					Original	Regenerated
1.	0.0	R.T.*	40	Pinkish white	0.38	0.20
2.	2.0	-do-	40	Pinkish white	0.45	0.20
3.	3.0	-do-	40	Shining pinkish white	0.52	0.52
4.	5.0	-do-	40	White	0.42	0.22
5.	9.0	-do-	40	Dull white	0.36	0.18
6.	11.0	-do-	40	Dull white	0.20	0.10
7.	2.0	40	40	Pinkish white	0.40	0.22
8.	9.0	40	40	Dull white	0.34	0.18
9.	3.0	R.T.	80	Dull white	0.45	0.40
10.	3.0	-do-	100	Dull white	0.42	0.40

* R.T. = Room temp.

NOTES

TABLE 2—THERMAL STABILITY OF STANNIC SILICO SELENITE

Temp. °C	Colour	Ion-exchange capacity for K ⁺ (meq/g)	Gain/loss in ion-exchange capacity (%)
40	Shining pinkish white	0.52	0.00
100	Pinkish white	0.68	+30.7
200	Dull white	0.64	+23.0
300	Dull white	0.60	+15.3
400	Grey	0.60	+15.3
500	Black	0.40	-23.0
600	Black	0.22	-57.6
700	Black	0.08	-84.6
800	Charcoal	0.02	-96.1

the gain is about 15%. Above 500°, the ion-exchange capacity tends to decrease and a loss of 96% is observed at 800°. This exchanger should therefore prove useful upto 500°. The thermogravimetric studies show that the weight loss in H⁺ form of the exchanger is greater than in K⁺ form. This is so because in the K⁺ form removal of water molecules by condensation is not possible and hence weight loss is only due to the removal of external water molecules.

Distribution coefficients (Table 3) for some metal ions in demineralised water were determined by the usual method. On the basis of these values quantitative separations of Cu²⁺ from Zn²⁺ and Cu²⁺ from Mn²⁺ were achieved experimentally on stannic silico selenite columns. Zn²⁺ and Mn²⁺ were eluted with 1% HNO₃ solution; Cu²⁺ retained on the column was eluted with 3% HNO₃ + 1 M NH₄NO₃ solution.

TABLE 3—DISTRIBUTION COEFFICIENTS OF METAL IONS ON STANNIC SILICO SELENITE

Metal ions	K _d value (ml/g)	
	Water	10 ⁻² M HNO ₃
Cu ²⁺	300.0	300.0
Zn ²⁺	11.4	6.2
Mn ²⁺	1.0	0.2
Hg ²⁺	168.0	98.0
Co ²⁺	4.2	1.2
Pb ²⁺	100.0	60.0
Ni ²⁺	2.4	0.6
Fe ²⁺	2.0	0.8
UO ₂ ²⁺	350.0	100.0
VO ₂ ²⁺	150.0	86.0
Al ³⁺	6.2	2.0
La ³⁺	100.0	78.0
Ce ³⁺	120.0	80.0

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